

Stability Constants of Cobalt-, Nickel- and Zinc(II) Complexes of some Tetradentate Imine-phenol Ligands

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The stability constants of bivalent Co, Ni and Zn with Schiff base derived ligands have been determined potentiometrically by Calvin-Bjerrum technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti and spectrophotometrically by Job's method of continuous variation in 80% (v/v) DMSO-water medium at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and ionic strength of 0.2 mol dm^{-3} .

The present communication is devoted to potentiometric investigation of complex formation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with four biologically important imine-phenol ligands *N,N'*-bis(2-hydroxybenzyl)-1,2-diaminoethane (1), *N,N'*-bis(2-hydroxybenzyl)-1,3-diaminopropane (2), *N,N'*-bis(2-hydroxyacetophenone-1,2-diaminoethane (3), *N,N'*-bis(2-hydroxyacetophenone-1,3-diaminopropane (4) at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in DMSO-water medium at an ionic strength of 0.2 M (KNO_3)¹. DMSO-water medium is used due to low solubility of the ligand and its metal complexes in water and other aquo-nonaqueous mixed solvent media².

- 1; $n = 0$, $R = \text{H}$ 3; $n = 0$, $R = \text{CH}_3$
2; $n = 1$, $R = \text{H}$ 4; $n = 1$, $R = \text{CH}_3$

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability and metal-ligand stability constants have been calculated potentiometrically by half-integral and graphical method³, and are given in Table 1. All the four ligands (1-4) show two dissociable protons corresponding to the two phenolic OH groups (K_2^{H} and K_3^{H}).

In addition, the K_4^{H} and K_3^{H} values (Table 1) correspond to the deprotonation of the protonated forms of the ligands which are formed on acidification of ligands. The $\log K^{\text{H}}$ values of the ligands 1-4 are found to follow the order: $1 > 2 > 3 > 4$. Lower K^{H} values of 3 and 4 might be due to electron-releasing CH_3 groups⁴. The K^{H} values of compound containing ethano-bridge is higher than that of a compound containing propano-bridge. The ethano-bridge has two CH_2 groups having lower inductive effect than the propano-bridge which has three CH_2 groups. Again, it can be explained on the basis of steric effect. The compound having propano-bridge is more strained and hence has a low $\log k$ value.

The stability constants of the metal complexes with the ligands 3 and 4 are found to be lower than those for the ligands 1 and 2. This may be due to the presence of electron-donating methyl group making N and O atoms more basic⁵. The presence of methyl group near the donor atoms might also possess steric effect making the complex comparatively less stable. On comparing the $\log K^{\text{M}}$ values for compounds 1 and 2, and 3 and 4 it seems that $\log K_1^{\text{M}} > \log K_2^{\text{M}}$ and $\log K_3^{\text{M}} > \log K_4^{\text{M}}$. This is contrary to the order of basicity of ligands, but complex formation is due to interplay of several factors, viz. steric factor, solvent effect, basicity, etc., and fortuitous combinatory of these factors may lead to the above order of the stability constant.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, 1,2-diaminoethane and 1,3-diaminopropane (all Ranbaxy) were used after purification. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ ligand solutions were prepared in DMSO and CO_2 -free distilled water.

The ligands were synthesized^{6,7} by condensing 2 equiv. of salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehyde with 1 equiv. of diamine in ethanol, and characterized by mass, ir and nmr spectral data.

Potentiometric titration : Titrations of ligands 1-4 as well as 1 : 1 M(II)-1, -2, -3 and -4 ($2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ each) in aqueous DMSO mixture (80%, v/v) with a relatively high concentrated NaOH solution ($0.103 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were

TABLE 1-PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF IMINE-PHENOL COMPLEXES*

(i) pKH values :

Ligand	$\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$	$\text{p}K_3^{\text{H}}$	$\text{p}K_4^{\text{H}}$	$\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$
1	3.79	5.63	8.95	11.47
2	3.55	5.51	8.38	10.89
3	3.52	4.98	8.28	10.76
4	3.44	4.70	8.18	10.49

(ii) Metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K$) values :

Ligand	Co^{II}	Ni^{II}	Zn^{II}
1	9.17	9.50	9.05
2	9.10	9.39	8.98
3	8.62	8.70	8.39
4	8.27	8.55	8.05

*Limits of error : ± 0.02 to 0.50 in log scale.

performed at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹. Constant ionic strength was maintained with 0.2 M KNO₃ keeping the total volume constant at 25 ml.

In order to account for the difference in acidity, basicity, dielectric constant and ion activities in partially aqueous solutions relative to the pure aqueous one, the pH values of the former solutions were corrected by making use of the reported procedure⁸. $\text{pH}^* = \text{pH}(\text{R}) - \delta$, where pH^* is the corrected reading, $\text{pH}(\text{R})$ the pH-meter reading obtained in partially aq. solutions, where pH-meter was standardized using aqueous buffers.

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